

THE IMAGES OF THE LOVER AND THE RIVAL IN SAKKOKI'S POETRY

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Annotation: The article examines the ways in which the images of the lover (‘āshiq) and the rival (raqīb) are represented and interpreted in Sakkoki’s ghazals. Through an analysis of selected poems, it explores the artistic functions, symbolic meanings, and ideological significance of these two central figures within the poet’s lyrical world. Particular attention is given to the lover as the embodiment of sincerity, devotion, and spiritual suffering, and to the rival as a force that obstructs union and intensifies the lover’s emotional trials.

Keywords: ghazal, valuable, rival, ashik, ishk, beloved one, heart

Sakkoki is one of the prominent poets of classical Uzbek literature. Unfortunately, very little information about his life and works has survived. Alisher Navoi mentions Sakkoki in his works “*Majolis un-Nafois*” and “*Muhokamat al-Lugatayn*” among the Turkic-speaking poets who lived during the reign of Shah Rukh. In particular, in the section “*Khutba-i Davovin*” (“Introduction to the Divans”), Navoi expresses the following views about the poet: “...Among the most eloquent representatives of the Uyghur literary idiom and the most accomplished stylists of the Turkic language were Mawlana Sakkoki and Mawlana Lutfi. The former’s sweet and graceful poetry attained extraordinary fame in Turkistan, whereas the latter’s refined ghazals spread extensively throughout Iraq and Khorasan. The divans of both poets were extant”¹.

These sources provide valuable insight into Sakkoki’s lifetime, his literary activity, and the position he occupied within the literary milieu of the fifteenth century, demonstrating that he was a poet of stature comparable to that of Lutfi. Furthermore, the poet Yakini, in his munazara entitled “*O’q va Yoy*” (“The Arrow and the Bow”), describes Sakkoki as “the mujtahid of the Turkic (Uzbek) poets,” that is, a zealous, pioneering, and leading poet among his contemporaries. Likewise, Shaykh Ahmad Tarazi, in “*Funun al-Balagha*”, provides information concerning the period in which the poet lived, his literary activity, and his place in the literary life of the fifteenth century, praising him with the honorific epithets “*Majma’ al-‘Aql*” (“Assembly of Intellect”) and “*Zahir al-Muta’akhhirin*” (“The Eminent One among the Later Poets”).

According to some sources, the poet spent part of his life at the court of Mirzo Ulughbek. However, other accounts suggest that he may have lived in the city of Sabron under the patronage of Arslon Khoja, who served as Ulughbek’s governor (naib) there. These accounts remain largely conjectural, as definitive historical evidence concerning this period of the poet’s life has not survived.² In particular, drawing on the edition of “*Funun al-Balagha*” prepared for publication by Abduqodir Hayitmetov, Mashhura Hasanova, in discussing Sakkoki’s pen names and appellations, argues that the poet not only resided in Sabron for a certain period of his life but was also born there. On this basis, she presents evidence suggesting that the nisba “*Sabroniy*” rightfully belongs to the poet, linking it to his place of origin and reinforcing the view that Sabron was both his birthplace and an important center in his life and literary career.³ At this point, it is worth

¹ Навоий А. МАТ, 20 томлик, 1-том, -Тошкент, Фан, 2002.

² Ҳайитметов А. Темурийлар даври ўзбек адабиёти, – Тошкент, 1996.

³ Ҳасанова М. Саккокий (Сайронийми? Саброний?!), – *Шарқ юлдузи*, 2011.

considering several plausible observations made by the author concerning the poet's pen name. As is well known, *Sakkoki* was the poet's literary pseudonym, while his actual name remains unknown. The pen name is derived from the word *sakkok* ("knife-maker" or "cutler"). It is therefore possible that the poet came from a family of craftsmen. According to Mashhura Hasanova, Sakkoki did not compose poetry under the pseudonym *Sayroniy*; rather, this attribution arose as a result of a scribal error made by a copyist. The word *Sayroniy* is written in the Arabic script as "سارونيد", whereas *Sabroniy* appears as "سارونيد". The only distinction between the two forms lies in the letters *yā'* (ي) and *bā'* (ب), which differ by a single dot. Consequently, it is entirely plausible that the word was copied incorrectly in a manuscript and that, owing to the addition of one extra dot, *Sabroniy* was transformed into *Sayroniy*. Such scribal inaccuracies are common in manuscript transmission and may account for the emergence of the latter form.

Mawlana Sakkoki was a native of Mawarannahr (Transoxiana). The people of Samarkand hold him in great esteem and speak of him with the highest praise...⁴ from his words, it can be seen that the poet mainly worked in Samarkand, the center of Transoxiana. However, it is known that he lived in other places from time to time. Унинг девонида учрайдиган қуйидаги байт фикримизни далиллайди:

*Dasht elidin Hoji Tarhonga yetushsa bu g'azal,
Tark etar har bahtiya osuda dunyosin Saroy...*

However, it remains unclear whether the "Dasht" mentioned here refers to Dasht-i Kipchak, to Dashtak in the vicinity of Bukhara, to Dashtak-i Bolo near Samarkand, or to an entirely different locality altogether.

The date of Sakkoki's birth is likewise unknown. It is generally presumed that he was born during the second half of the fourteenth century, most likely in the final quarter of that century.⁵ Many sources indicate that this assumption is based on the following lines from an ode written in honor of Amir Temur's grandson, Khalil Sultan (reigned 1405–1409):

*Tarixqa sekkiz yuz dag'ū o'n erdi-yu qadr axshomi,
Bir oy tug'ildi dunyoda kim mamlakatda xon bo'ldi.*

The poet emphasizes that the night of the prince's birth was the Night of Power. This date corresponds to the year 810 (1407–1408 AD) according to the Hijri calendar. Considering that Sakkoki wrote his ode when he was already quite experienced in his craft, approximately at the age of 30, the above assumptions regarding his birth date are close to the truth.

Alongside his ghazals, Sakkoki's qasidas in the Uzbek language dedicated to Mirzo Ulugh Beg, Arslon Khoja Tarkhan, and Khoja Muhammad Parsa represent a significant achievement in the development of this poetic genre within Uzbek literature. In one of his qasidas devoted to Ulugh Beg, the poet speaks not only about his illustrious ancestor, renowned as both a ruler and a scholar, but also about himself. These poems, in turn, contain valuable historical information and serve as important sources for the study of the period in which they were composed.

*Falak yillar kerak aylansa-yu keltursa ilkiga,
Meningdek shoiri turk-u seningdek shohi dononi! —*

Unfortunately, it is impossible to fully assess Sakkoki's literary heritage, since only the last part of his divan has survived to us. The date of the poet's death is also uncertain. There are only some assumptions. They are associated with Navoi's arrival in Samarkand. It is known that the great poet visited this city twice, but did not meet Sakkoki. This gives grounds for the opinion that Sakkoki died before 1467-1469.

4 Навоий А. МАТ, 20 томлик, 13-том.-Тошкент: Фан, 2002.

5 Маллаев Н.. Ўзбек адабиёти тарихи. 1-китоб. Т., «Ўқитувчи» нашриёти, 1965.

It is known that two manuscript copies of Sakkoki's divan have survived. However, both copies are incomplete, particularly with regard to the section containing the ghazals. One of these manuscripts is preserved in the British Museum in London under catalogue number 2079 and is believed to have been copied in the mid-sixteenth century. The other copy, held at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan under manuscript number 7685, is known to have been transcribed in 1937 by a scribe named Shoislom. However, the original source manuscript on which this copy was based has not been fully identified. The only available note, found on folio 54 (the final page) of the divan, states that the manuscript was copied from a handwritten exemplar provided by Abdurauf Fitrat, without offering any further clarification regarding the provenance of that original source. The divan contains thirteen qasidas and fifty-two ghazals. The differences between the two surviving manuscripts are not particularly substantial, and both preserve only a portion of Sakkoki's ghazals. In accordance with the traditional arrangement of a divan, the collection opens with a single *hamd* (poem in praise of God), followed by one *na't* (poem in praise of the Prophet Muhammad), and then eleven panegyric qasidas. Of these qasidas, one is dedicated to Khoja Muhammad Parsa, another to Khalil Sultan, four to Mirzo Ulugh Beg, one to Shah Rukh (although in the divan this poem is mistakenly headed "In Praise of Ulugh Beg Mirza"), and four to Arslon Khoja Tarkhan. Altogether, the qasidas comprise 407 couplets, or 814 poetic lines.

In the poet's *Selected Works*, prepared for publication in 1958 by Qayum Munirov, fifty-six ghazals were included, whereas the volume *Hayot Vasfi*, published in the "Uzbek Literature Garden" series, contains fifty-five ghazals. Both editions also include the qasida with the refrain (*radif*) "Keldi" ("Has Come"). Sakkoki's divan has been republished several times, and certain discrepancies can be observed among these editions. For instance, one edition identifies four qasidas dedicated to Mirzo Ulugh Beg, while another, relying on the heading "In Praise of Ulugh Beg Mirza," counts the qasida actually devoted to Shah Rukh among Ulugh Beg's panegyrics, thereby increasing the total number of qasidas dedicated to Ulugh Beg to five.⁶

In addition to the ghazals contained in the poet's divan, various sources preserve additional ghazals and individual couplets attributed to Sakkoki. The number of such poems exceeds ten. In particular, a manuscript miscellany numbered 4757, housed in the Ayasofya Collection of the Suleymaniye Library, contains the texts of three ghazals bearing the poet's pen name. These poems were copied by Shaykhzada Abdurazzoq Bakhshi. The three lyrical works were later published by the Turkish scholar Osman Fikri Sertkaya.⁷ They begin with the following lines:

1. "Ey zulfi zanjirim biror devonalarni yod qil..."
2. "Ey mening ko'nglumni zulfitek parishon aylagan..."

⁶ Жўраев Ж., Хатамов Ў. Мавлоно Саккокий:– Тошкент: "Bookmany print" нашриёти, 2024. – 84 б.

⁷ Эрослан Камол. Мавлоно Саккокий. Анқара, 1999.

Мазкур китобдан шоирнинг 2 та муножоти, 11 та қасида ва уларнинг туркча табдили киритилган. Бундан ташқари мазкур девондан бизда мавжуд бўлган қўлёзмадан тушиб қолган газаллари билан бирга шоирнинг жами 60 та газали ўрин олган.

3. “Ey orazi bargi gulu vey qomati sarvi suman...”

Furthermore, in “Majolis un-Nafois”, Alisher Navoi cites the following matla’ (opening couplet), which is not included in Sakkoki’s extant divan, and explicitly attributes it to the poet, thereby confirming its authorship:

*Ne noz-u bu ne shevadur, ey jodu ko ‘zhluk sho ‘xshang,
Kabki dariy, tovsda yo ‘q, albatta, bu raftoru rang.*

In the recent “Bow and Arrow” debate:

*Jonim fido bo ‘lsun sening g ‘amzang o ‘qina nechakim,
Har necha qoshing egmasi o ‘qtek bo ‘yumni “yo(y)” qilur.*

It is indicated that it belongs to Sakkoki. Such verses are also found in “Funun ul-Balogha” by Sheikh Ahmad Tarazi. Including:

*Ey soching shaydo ko ‘ngullarning savodi a ‘zami,
Halqa-halqa ruhning sarmanzalidur har xami...*

*Soldi kuygan ko ‘ngluma ul englari gulnor nor,
Bo ‘lmadi hargiz manga ul dilbari ayyor yor...*

*Bo ‘stonda gul yuzungg ‘a o ‘zni har dam o ‘xshatib,
Bo ‘lmish araq to g ‘arqu hanuz infioli bor...*

*Sanuvbaroki, sening labingda muncha xavos,
Kim ani so ‘rsa balodin topar jahonda xalos...*

*Yuzung guli muzayyan etar husn bog ‘ini,
Xoling savodi nahv qilur ko ‘z charog ‘ini...*

*Atlas erur saqollari, barcha bulutlari nasaj,
Garchiki durru donadur og ‘zini ochsa to ‘dasi...*

*Sarv ne had birla sarkashlik qilur qadding bila,
Bilgurur maydon ichinda har kishining poyasi...*

The following rubā’ī (quatrain), cited by Shaykh Ahmad Tarazi, is likewise attributed to Sakkoki and may be regarded as one of the poet’s works preserved outside his extant divan:

*Gulyuzungni ko ‘rsa bulbul dar chaman,
Kechib o ‘z savdosidin bo ‘lg ‘ay chu man.*

*Lablaringg ‘a teng tutar o ‘zni aqiq,
Bilmasu behuda so ‘zlar ul Yaman,*

These observations help clarify several important issues. First, as noted above, Sakkoki appears to have been known not only by the pen name Sakkoki but also by the appellation Sabroniy. Second, his literary activity was not confined to the genres of the ghazal and qasida; he also composed poetry in the rubā’ī form. However, the quatrain cited by Shaykh Ahmad Tarazi is not written in the conventional metre of the classical rubā’ī, but rather in a metre characteristic of the tuyuq genre. This suggests that, even before the time of Alisher Navoi, Turkic poetry already included works composed in both the rubā’ī and tuyuq forms. The principal distinction between these two genres lies in the nature of their rhyme: a tuyuq typically employs tajnīs (paronomastic or homonymous rhyme), whereas a rubā’ī does not necessarily do so. A similar phenomenon can be observed in the rubā’īs included in “Sensan Sevarim” by Lutfi.

The ghazal occupies a central place in Sakkoki’s poetic oeuvre. In the extant manuscripts of his divan, the sequence of ghazals arranged according to the letters of the alphabet – from *alif* to

nun – has not been preserved in its entirety. The ghazal section begins with two poems whose *radif* (refrain) ends in the letter *n*, after which the poems continue in alphabetical order. Interestingly, no ghazals ending with the letter *vav* (*v*) are found in the surviving manuscripts. The ghazal portion of the divan concludes with forty ghazals ending in the letters *sin* (*s*) and *ya* (*y*).

Sakkoki's ghazals have been interpreted in different ways by various scholars. A number of literary critics maintain that a central theme of his poetry is the portrayal of human emotions, particularly sincere love between individuals. This love is presented not merely as a personal sentiment but as one closely intertwined with an appreciation of life, the beauty of nature, and noble human virtues. The literary scholar Naim Karimovich Mallaev, in his analysis of several of Sakkoki's ghazals, observes that they celebrate earthly love, fidelity, loyalty, joy, and cheerfulness. At the same time, he notes that the poet strongly condemns hypocrisy, moral corruption, faithlessness, and arrogance, thereby underscoring the ethical dimension of Sakkoki's lyrical vision.

In the majority of Sakkoki's ghazals, three principal figures recur consistently: the lover (*'āshiq*), the beloved (*ma'shūqa*), and the rival (*raqīb*). Among these, the lover occupies the central position and serves as the primary lyrical protagonist, shaping the emotional atmosphere of the poet's verse. The lover is portrayed as sincere, faithful, and pure-hearted. He is utterly captivated by the prospect of union with the beloved and suffers intensely from the pain of separation. His deepest aspiration is to attain the beloved's favor and grace and to experience the joys of love. Yet the path of love is fraught with obstacles, anguish, and sorrow, all of which he must endure with patience and devotion.

The ghazal beginning with the line "Quydurdi ko'ngul mamlakatin yor firoqi" ("The beloved's separation set the kingdom of the heart aflame") stands apart from many of the poet's other works. Unlike his predominantly secular love lyrics, this poem possesses a distinctly mystical and Sufi-oriented character. It may therefore be regarded as one of Sakkoki's more individual and experimental attempts to engage with the tradition of love-mystical (*ishqiyyat*) poetry.

Kuydurdi ko'ngul mamlakatin yor firoqi,
O'tdek suvni so'ngni g'am o'tini uchrali soqi⁸,

Here, the poet portrays separation from the beloved as a destructive, consuming force. Through the experience of *firāq* (separation), the "kingdom" or "realm" of the heart is set ablaze and laid waste, symbolizing the devastation of the lover's inner world. The grief resulting from this separation is depicted as so powerful that it surpasses both water and fire in its intensity. The imagery is metaphorical, representing the profound anguish that overwhelms the lover's heart. From a mystical perspective, the separation that burns the lover from within may also be interpreted as the suffering caused by the inability to attain union with the Divine Beloved. In this reading, the pain of separation transcends earthly love and becomes a symbol of spiritual longing. One point, however, remains clear: love is presented as a purifying fire, a force that refines the soul through suffering and transforms the seeker on the path toward spiritual perfection.

Oshiq boshini kesub tu ul shoh yasoq olmusi,
Yaraliq boshim orzusi erur xud bu yasoqi.

Love is so strong that if the lover (*king*) commands, the lover is ready to sacrifice himself, even considering it an honor to lose his head. This surrender also reflects the idea of *fano* (self-annihilation) in Sufism, the complete defeat of the ego.

⁸ Муниров Қ. Саккокий. Танланган асарлар: – Т., Бадиий адабиёт нашриёти, 1958. – 84 б.

Yorimni ko'raturmoq uchun umr tilayurmen,
Yo'q ersa menga nega kerak umr uzoqi.

The value of life is tied to a partner. Without a partner, there is no point in dreaming of a long life. This is the central point of the philosophy of love: without love, life is meaningless.

Yorimning erur qaddi chinor, enlari gulnor,
Jonlarga safo berur uning husniyu toqi.

Here, the physical beauty of the yor is depicted through the images of nature, such as maple, flower, and sapofa. Husn can be not only external, but also internal light.

Shod bo'lma raqib o'ldi tiyo oshiqi miskin,
Barchaga tuzi kelgusidur davr ahqi.

Let not the rival rejoice – the poor lover has passed away, deprived of comfort and peace. Yet time tests every individual according to its own justice. In these lines, one finds an acknowledgment of, and a belief in, the ultimate justice of the world: although the lover suffers and perishes, the course of time will eventually render a fair judgment upon all.

Dunyo g'amini qo'y, bu jahon saltanatini,
Ishq ichida ul oy oshiq o'larsen chu bayqi.

This passage emphasizes the transitory nature of life's pleasures and worldly glory, portraying them as fleeting and illusory as a mirage in the desert. The deeper meaning, however, lies in love and the suffering of the heart. Within this perspective, to perish in the path of love is regarded not as a misfortune but as a form of fulfillment and blessedness.

*Hasrat bilan Sakkokiy xud o'ldi, sen zo'n qol,
Ishrat bilan, ey shohi jahon, dunyoda boqi.*

Sakkoki passed away in pain and sorrow. His death should serve as a lesson to those who are addicted to worldly materialism. Here one can sense a moral, mystical admonition: life is measured by spirituality, not pride.

The poet's ghazals are of high artistic quality: rich in metaphors and similes, skillfully applied poetic techniques, fluent in style, simple and beautiful in language. He draws his metaphors and similes mainly from the surrounding visible objects, folk language, traditions, and customs.

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